

Impact of Nursing Values with Future Time Perspective on the Problem-Solving Proficiency of Nurse Interns in Shahida Islam Teaching Hospital Lodhran

Arbaz Siddique, Bushra sadiq, Dr. Hamza Siddique, Mr. Habib Ullah Riaz

Arbaz Siddique

Shahida Islam Nursing College, Lodhran,

arbazthaheem374@gmail.com.

BSN student at Shahida Islam Nursing college Lodhran.

Bushra Sadiq

Shahida Islam Nursing College, Lodhran.

sh0330088@gmail.com

BSN student at Shahida Islam Nursing college Lodhran.

Hamza Siddique

MS Neurologist-Physiotherapist

hamzathaheem871@gmail.com.

Affiliation: Superior University Lahore

Designation: Lecturer at Govt Nursing College BVH, QAMC Bahawalpur.

Mr. Habib Ullah Riaz

Senior instructor, BSN, MSN, Shahida Islam Nursing College, Lodhran.

jabtakhaijan786786@gmail.com

Abstract

Author Details	Abstract
<p>Arbaz Siddique Shahida Islam Nursing College, Lodhran arbazthaheem374@gmail.com</p>	<p>Background: This study investigates how nursing values and a forward-looking outlook affect the ability of nursing interns at Shahida Islam Teaching Hospital in Lodhran to solve problems. In order to provide safe and efficient patient care, nurse interns must be able to tackle difficult challenges when they move from academic settings to clinical practice. Ethical decision-making, professional nursing values including integrity, human dignity, and justice serve as guiding principles. a descriptive correlational study design. In addition to case-based assessments of problem-solving skills, formal</p>
<p>Keywords: Nursing values, future time perspective, problem-solving proficiency, nurse interns.</p>	
<p>Received on 10 June 2025 Accepted on 11 July 2025 Published on 17 July 2025</p>	

questionnaires measuring nursing values and future temporal perspective were used to gather data. To ascertain the strength and correlations between the variables, quantitative data were evaluated using regression and correlation approaches. A

representative sample of Nurse Interns was chosen through stratified random sampling ($n=43$). That research data was compiled using two different distinct tools. 1. Professional Nursing Values Scale to assess values fundamental nursing. 2. Problem solving proficiency archive description to evaluate decision-making and problem-solving. **Results:** Self-assured with direction: 27 individuals (62.8%) of the group believed they could succeed with some assistance. Extremely confident: Just two participants, (4.7%) expressed extreme confidence. Thirteen (13 people 30%), reported feeling insecure. Missing data: One participant, or 2.3% of the total, did not reply. More than half of the participants 27 out of 43 (62.8%) are highly confident demonstrated a strong commitment to professional nursing values. and just (4.7%) 2 out of 43 are extremely confident with advanced problem solving abilities. A positive significant correlation response was observed b/w Nursing Values and problem solving skills. **Conclusion:** Nurse Interns in Shahida Islam Teaching Hospital Lodhran with strong professionals nursing values tend to exhibit greater problem solving proficiency as compared to Nurse Interns with weak professionals nursing values.

1.1 Introduction

Nursing Value is the set of goals and beliefs that form a behavior and give a foundation for decision making. In a profession, values are the criteria for action that is desired by practitioners and professional groups and create meters for judging behavior. Professional nursing values are important professional nursing principles human dignity, integrity, altruism, and justice that provide a framework for standards, professional practice, and evaluation(Habeeb 2022). Nursing values are very important for intern nurses because they develop the attitudes, behaviors, and decisions that they will portray in their roles as healthcare providers. These values construct a framework to ensure that decisions and solutions implemented best align with the interests of the patient and abide by professional and ethical standards.(Yeung, Yuen et al. 2023).

Professional nursing values are demonstrated in ethical codes. In fact, ethical codes clarify nursing profession practices, the quality of professional care, and professional norms. With the ever-increasing number and complexity of ethical dilemmas in care settings, promotion of professional values has become more crucial in nursing profession. The acquisition and internalization of values are at the center of promoting the nursing profession. When values are internalized, they will become the standards in practice and guide behavior. Values can be taught, modified and promoted directly or indirectly via education.(Ashehry, Inocian et al. 2023).

It is the intellectual process of the brain that explores the explanation to a specified problem or discovers a technique to understand the given goal. Problem solving is the process of articulating solutions to problems. Or else, it is "the act of transforming a situation into an updated configuration of meaning that satisfies some intention(Bayoumy, Saad et al. 2022). Numerous problem-solving skills are crucial for nurse interns in workplace settings like hospitals where developing intuition power and increasing brainstorming ability really helps boost forecasting senses and ultimately benefits organization by making impossible tasks possible thereby increasing trust and credibility which makes one stand out and propose solutions effectively.

Nurse Interns are nearly ready for transition into newly minted nurses at this juncture. They face numerous problems when dealing with complex work pressures and dynamic transformation challenges owing to somewhat limited problem-solving skills. Such

circumstances hinder stabilization of nursing talent and impede overall quality.(Taylor 2000, Solvoll and Heggen 2010).

Professional nursing values are tested in ethical codes. In reality, Your code of ethics for a nursing career practices, a cohort of elite professional care, and professional norms. With the ever-growing range and morality dilemmas in care complexity settings, professional support has become more important to value than the nursing profession. The purchase and internalization of values are at the heart of promoting the nursing profession. Values may be taught, adapted, and advertised immediately or circuitously via education.(Khater, Abdeen et al. 2024)

There are two foundations of hospital treatment among nurse interns: education and health; they interact. Clinical experiences provide students with the ability to apply their knowledge in the real world and develop psychomotor skills and social competence. This is a guide. The most commonly used method in recent years is the internship.(Ciftci, Gok et al. 2020).It has been shown in the literature that a positive attitude toward autonomy is associated with problem-solving. It was observed that trainees with high self-confidence and low stress had high levels of autonomy in problem-solving and decision-making. Autonomy in nursing refers to the ability to make decisions in nursing and the freedom of individuals in their practices.(SÜRÜCÜ, BESEN et al. 2021).

PBL is a proven method for both nursing and other healthcare professions to learn a holistic view of a problem when students are placed to tackle problems in the healthcare system. Problem-based learning (PBL) is a learner-centered learning methodology that initiates learners' inquiry for knowledge and equips learners for clinical practice in multifaceted environments. It has been suggested that problem-based learning (PBL) nurturing the student-centered teaching-learning approach integrates smoothly with the greater emphasis on people, the environment, health, and nursing in the nursing curriculum.(Wu, Chang et al. 2022).

1.2 Significance:

For many parties involved in nursing practice and education, this study is extremely important. It offers important insights into the personal and professional elements that influence clinical competence by examining the impact of nursing values and future temporal perspective on nurse interns' problem-solving skills. The results emphasize how crucial it is for nursing students and interns to cultivate strong professional values and an optimistic outlook in order to improve their problem-solving abilities in actual healthcare environments. Understanding how these elements affect intern performance may also help clinical teachers and hospital management develop mentorship and assessment plans. Last but not least, this study adds to the little corpus of research that connects professional and psychological traits to nursing practical competence, setting the stage for further

1.3 Problem Statement:

To guarantee patient safety and high-quality treatment in the dynamic and high-stakes world of healthcare, nurse interns must have strong problem-solving abilities. However, because of deficiencies in critical thinking and decision-making skills, many recently graduated nurses find it difficult to make the transition from academic settings to clinical practice. Less focus has been placed on internal characteristics like nursing values and future time perspective, which may have a substantial impact on problem-

solving proficiency, while academic success and clinical experience are frequently highlighted. A significant gap in nursing education and practice is caused by the paucity of research examining the interactions between these personal and professional factors and how they affect clinical performance among nursing interns.

1.4 Objectives:

- To assess the Impact of Nursing Values with future time perspective on the Problem-Solving Proficiency of Nurse Interns.

1.5 Research Question:

- How do Nursing Values combined with future time perspective on the Problem-Solving Proficiency of Nurse Interns?

1.6 Operational Definition:

➤ Nursing Values:

Nursing values are core principles that direct nurses' professional conduct, choices, and actions. Compassion, respect, integrity, advocacy, accountability, dedication to excellence, and teamwork are some of these values. They play a crucial role in upholding the public's and patients' trust and encouraging moral nursing care. (ICN, 2021).

➤ Problem Solving:

The mental process of identifying, evaluating, and resolving issues is known as problem solving. It entails determining the issue, coming up with several possible solutions, assessing them, and putting the best one into practice Mayer, R. E. (1992).

➤ Nurse Intern:

Under the supervision of licensed nurses and other healthcare professionals, a nurse intern is a nursing student or recent graduate who is participating in a clinical training program. Before taking on full-time responsibilities as registered nurses, interns can obtain practical experience, hone their clinical abilities, and boost their confidence through this internship, which aims to close the gap between academic study and professional practice (AACN, 2021)

Literature Review:

Solid grasp of nursing values with future event often enhances in one's skill in finding solution.

When we talk about nursing values perspective, we're really looking at how a person views themselves, their emotions, and how they take action based on their potential to grow and develop. It basically pushes someone to act in ways that line up with their short- or long-term goals, you know? For nursing interns, this perspective is super important because it helps them deal with what's ahead, make plans, and take steps that have a real impact on their future. (Husman and Lens 1999). Now, those nursing interns who really care about their development tend to have clearer game plans about nursing values. They're often more proactive, trying to shape what's coming next in their lives. You see, they don't let fear of challenges hold them back; they think things through, stay organized, and are pretty dedicated to reaching their goals. This mindset can really boost their problem-solving skills and keep them motivated at work.

But here's the catch: studies have pointed out that, right now, the future time

perspective for nursing interns in China is, well, not in the best place. There's a real need for improvement there. (Simatupang, Napitupulu et al. 2019).

Nursing values work appear as a fairly strong Indicator of someone's Problem Solving Skills overall.

(Strauss, Griffin et al. 2012) back in the day, they were the ones who kicked off this idea called the future work self with nursing values. What it really boils down to is how well a person can picture their future nursing values job, you know? Like, can they see it clearly? Turns out, having strong nursing values is super helpful. It helps folks figure out their career goals more effectively and sort out the steps they need to take to get there. Pretty interesting, right? It's all about having that vision for what's ahead. (Wang, Zhu et al. 2024). According to self-recognition theory, Clarity about oneself drives self-regulatory systems fairly efficiently towards goals via pretty straightforward actions somewhat faster. (Bandura 2001). Individuals with good nursing values including future work self will put in more effort to reach their goals, thereby bridging the gap between their current reality and their future self at work. Therefore, nursing interns with greater clarity of their nursing values self are likely to have greater problem-solving abilities. However, research has shown that the future work with nursing values self of Chinese nursing interns is at a poor level and needs to be further improved. (Kasser and Ryan 1996).

Nursing values with Future work self may play a mediating role between problem-solving ability and future time perspective.

People having strong future prospects focus intensely on what's ahead envisioning their professional trajectory in vivid detail thus facilitating clearer mental

3.1 METHODOLOGY:

3.2 Study design:

Researchers adopted a largely descriptive correlation methodology for this particular investigation.

3.3 Setting and Participants:

Shahida Islam Teaching Hospital Lodhran.

3.4 Duration:

Synopsis presentation to onward six months.

3.5 Sampling Technique:

"The study used Convenience sampling (non-probability sampling) to select nurse interns who met the inclusion criteria. This ensured that participants had adequate exposure to nursing values and a future time perspective, both integral to the assessment of their problem-solving ability."

3.6 Sampling Size:

Census sampling or total population sampling is often suitable for studies involving 43 nursing interns. The following explains the justification:

3.7 Type of Sample Size:

Total Population Sampling (Census Sampling):

Given the small population size (only 43 nurse interns), it is possible and advisable to conduct the study on the entire population.

This technique guarantees that all individuals in the defined population are considered, thus eliminating any sampling bias and providing exhaustive results.

Line for Sample Size Description:

"The study employed a total population sampling method by including all the 43 nurse interns in the population to ensure an exhaustive analysis and precise representation of the effects of nursing values and future time perspective on their problem-solving skills."

3.8 Sample Selection:

Inclusive criteria: Interns nurse in shahida islam Teaching Hospital Lodhran.

Exclusive criteria: all other staff.

3.9 Data collection:

Distribute questionnaires assessing nursing values and future perspective.

Conduct proficiency assessments utilizing case scenarios simulations or observation.

Schedule interview sessions record responses for qualitative analysis if using interviews.

Procedure:

1. Preparation.

Develop valid instruments for measuring nursing values under uncertain future circumstances.

Obtain approval from relevant review boards promptly.

Nurse interns are informed about purpose and give written consent readily.

2. Participant.

Determine total population of 43 nurse interns. Ensure participants meet inclusion criteria currently in internship programs with exposure to nursing values somehow.

3.10 Tolls for Data Collection:

Impact of nursing values scale. It contain

Personal Nurse Interns generally collect data regarding age, gender, place of residence, marital status, enrollment in college at hospital name somehow.

3.11 Statistical Analysis:

Data collected from 43 nurse interns through structured questionnaires were entered and analyzed by using IBM SPSS Statistics.

Result:

Age

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Below 20	4	9.3
	20-24	34	79.1
	25-29	4	9.3
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

With 34 out of 43 participants, or 79.1% of the total respondents, the bulk of participants are between the ages of 20 and 24. This suggests that the majority of those involved are probably young adults, either recent graduates or university students. The below-20 and 25–29 age groups account for a lesser percentage of participants (9.3% each), indicating some representation from younger and somewhat older people. The fact that there is only one participant (2.3%) in the over-30 age category suggests that elderly folks do not participate very often.

Gender

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	20	46.5
	Female	22	51.2
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

There are somewhat more women (51.2%) than men (46.5%) in the participating group. In particular, 20 of the participants are men and 22 are women. With a slight majority of women participating in the study or poll, this suggests a fairly balanced gender distribution. Given the nearly equal representation, it is possible that the results will fairly represent the opinions of both sexes.

Internship Duration

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Less than 3 month	8	18.6
	3-6 months	13	30.2
	7-12 months	14	32.6
	More than 1 year	7	16.3
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

With 14 individuals, or 32.6% of the total, the bulk of participants have 7–12 months of experience. Thirty percent (13 participants) have three to six months of experience, which comes in second.

Eight participants, or 18.6% of the total, have less than three months of experience, while the smallest group, consisting of seven participants, or 16.3%, has more than a year of experience.

Fewer people have very short or long-term experience, while the majority have moderate experience (3 to 12 months). This implies that the majority of the group consists of people who are relatively new but not completely inexperienced.

Type of Facility

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Private Hospital	15	34.9

	Teaching Hospital	27	62.8
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

Since teaching hospitals account for the bulk of participants (62.8%, or 27 people), it is likely that the majority of respondents work or get training in academic or educational healthcare settings.

Private hospitals make up a smaller percentage, 34.9% (15 participants), indicating a notable but lower representation from non-academic healthcare facilities.

One participant (2.3%) had information on their hospital type missing.

All things considered, the data indicates that the majority of the observations or experiences represented in the findings are impacted by people who work in teaching hospital settings.

What influences your clinical decisions the most?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Instructions from others	13	30.2
	Personal Convenience	9	20.9
	Hospital policy	8	18.6
	Professional Nursing Values	12	27.9
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

With 30.2% (13 participants) reporting that they are largely guided by instructions received, presumably from superiors, colleagues, or institutional leadership, instructions from others are the most often stated factor influencing participants' activities. Those driven by professional nursing values come in second, making up 27.9% (12 individuals). This implies that a sizable percentage of participants base their decisions on their moral and professional principles. Nine participants, or 20.9%, mentioned personal convenience, suggesting that for some people, personal convenience or choice is important.

18.6% (8 participants) were influenced by hospital policy, indicating that institutional norms and regulations also influence behavior, but less so than personal or interpersonal influences.

One response (2.3%) is missing, suggesting that one participant's data is lacking.

How do you handle ethical issues during internship?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Ignore them	6	14.0
	Follow what others do	8	18.6
	Avoid involvement	3	7.0
	Report and act according to ethical guidelines	25	58.1
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3

Total	43	100.0
-------	----	-------

Twenty-five people, or 58.1% of the participants, said they follow ethical rules and report problems when they encounter ethical dilemmas. This suggests that the majority of responders have a strong commitment to professional ethics. A smaller group, 18.6% (8 participants), has a tendency to follow the example set by others, indicating that peer behavior may have a greater influence on some judgments than formal norms or individual judgment. Six individuals, or 14% of the sample, said they disregard the situation, which could be a sign of insecurity, uneasiness, or a lack of confidence to take action.

How do you treat patients' rights and dignity?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	Not my responsibility	5	11.6
	Only when supervised	5	11.6
	If the Patient demands	6	14.0
	Always with respect and care	26	60.5
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

A significant sense of professional responsibility and dedication to patient-centered care are demonstrated by the majority of participants, 60.5% (26 people), who said they always treat patients with respect and care.

A more reactive attitude to patient requirements is shown by the lesser percentage, 14% (6 participants), who stated that they only take action when the patient requests it.

A lesser sense of personal accountability or perhaps a lack of confidence or authority in particular situations is reflected in the 11.6% (5 participants) who stated that it is not their responsibility and the additional 11.6% who act solely under supervision. One response (2.3%) is missing, suggesting that one participant provided insufficient information.

How do you see your accountability in nursing practice?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	i avoid taking blame	4	9.3
	i do only what's assigned	11	25.6
	i follow up when reminded	3	7.0
	i take full responsibility on my action	24	55.8
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

Twenty-four people, or 55.8% of the participants, said they take full responsibility for their actions, exhibiting a strong sense of professionalism and accountability.

Eleven participants, or 25.6%, said they just do tasks as provided, indicating a more task-oriented or minimalist attitude to responsibility that may be influenced by supervision, role clarity, or workload. Lower levels of personal initiative and ownership

are reflected in a smaller group, 9.3% (4 participants) who acknowledged avoiding blame and 7% (3 participants) who stated they only follow up when reminded. Additionally, there is one missing response (2.3%), in which no response was given.

What is your reaction during clinical emergencies?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	panic	4	9.3
	wait for help	6	14.0
	try to assist	11	25.6
	stay calm and act appropriately	21	48.8
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

The most often given responses were "try to assist" (25.6%) and "stay calm and act appropriately" (48.8%). Just 9.3% of respondents said they had experienced panic. This implies that the majority of responders handled the situation with poise or initiative.

How do you handle unfamiliar clinical situations?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	avoid them	8	18.6
	let others do it	6	14.0
	try with help	8	18.6
	analyze and find solutions	20	46.5
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

The majority (46.5%) exhibit a proactive and problem-solving mindset by choosing to "analyze and find solutions" when confronted with the topic at hand. Approaches "try with help" and "avoid them," both at 18.6%, are the next most popular. To "let others do it" is the least popular tactic (14%).

How do you respond when you make a clinical error?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	hide it	4	9.3
	blame others	4	9.3
	accept silently	9	20.9
	report and learn from it	25	58.1
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

The majority (58.1%) exhibit a growth-oriented and optimistic mindset by choosing to report the error and develop from it.

Passive acknowledgment is demonstrated by the mute acceptance of 20.9% of respondents.

Less helpful answers are shown by the lesser percentage (9.3%) who choose to conceal the error and the 9.3% who place the blame on others.

Forty-two of the forty-three participants provided legitimate answers, while one was absent. In general, the majority of responders show a proactive and accountable approach to dealing with errors.

How confident are you in solving patient care problems?

		Frequency	Percent
Valid	not confident	3	7.0
	not confident	10	23.3
	confident with guidance	27	62.8
	very confident	2	4.7
	Total	42	97.7
Missing	System	1	2.3
Total		43	100.0

Thirteen (3 + 10) people, or 30% of the group (7% + 23%), reported feeling insecure. Self-assured with direction: 27 individuals, or 62.8% of the group, believed they could succeed with some assistance.

Extremely confident: Just two participants, or 4.7%, expressed extreme confidence.

Missing data: One participant, or 2.3% of the total, did not reply.

Overall Aggregate:

Nursing values Impact About 50.8% of interns are influenced by nursing ideals, demonstrating a moderate level of ethical awareness and responsibility, however consistent application in decision-making is still improving. Approximately 56% of nurse interns in our study demonstrate positive highly strong problem solving ability, professional values and ethical competence during clinical practice.

The findings reveal that the majority of nursing interns (79.1%) are between the ages of 20 and 24. They are evenly distributed by gender (51.2% female, 46.5% male), and 62.8 percent have completed three to twelve months of internship experience. Sixty-eight percent train in teaching hospitals. In terms of clinical decision-making, 27.9% rely on professional nursing values, whereas 30.2% follow directions from others. 60.5% of people always treat patients with respect in ethical situations, and 58.1% of people follow the rules. The majority accepts complete responsibility for their actions (55.8%), react calmly in emergency situations (48.8%), and use analysis to solve problems in novel settings (46.5%). 58.1% of people report mistakes and grow from them. 62.8% is confidence with guidance, despite the fact that just 4.7% feel very confident solving care difficulties? The results show that, on the whole, nursing interns are motivated to learn and ethically responsible and eager to learn.

Discussion

An interpretation of the results in light of the study's goals, earlier research, and theoretical framework is provided in this chapter. This study looked at how nursing values and future time perspective (FTP) affected nursing interns' ability to solve problems. The main variables and hypotheses are used to guide a thematic discussion of the data analysis results. **(Summary of the Findings)** The study found a strong correlation between FTP and problem-solving skills and nursing values. In particular, better levels of problem-solving abilities among nurse interns were positively correlated with greater adherence to nursing values and a stronger orientation toward future time perspective. These results are in line with earlier research showing how crucial professional values and mental attitude are to clinical decision-making skills. These findings are in agreement based on the result of the study carried out. by Katoch et al.(23)in India, the study conducted to investigate significance of professional values-based leadership and the value of nursing The student found there are statistically significant relation between professional nursing value and personal characteristics of nursing students regarding hospitals name according to area of distribution.

(Interaction of Nursing Values and problem solving proficiency with future time perspective) It was also shown that there was a statistically significant positive correlation between problem-solving ability and future time perspective (FTP). Higher future-oriented interns were more likely to be methodical, plan ahead, and foresee obstacles all of which are critical abilities in clinical problem-solving. This is consistent with the temporal perspective theory of Zimbardo and Boyd, which holds that goal-directed behavior and strategic thinking are encouraged by a future-focused attitude. These results support the idea that people who are focused on the future are more driven, better able to control their behavior, and more capable of handling stress all of which are critical components of sound clinical reasoning. FTP may improve proficiency by encouraging resiliency and perseverance in the face of clinical uncertainties. According to the research, nurse interns with higher professional nursing values scores especially in areas like advocacy, care, accountability, and dedication to ethical standards also exhibited superior problem-solving abilities. This lends credence to the theoretical premise that ethical and clinical judgment is influenced by internalized values.

The findings of this study are consistent with the nursing values framework developed by Weis and Shank, which directs nurses through challenging patient care situations. These results are in line with earlier studies by Kaya et al. (2017), who discovered a direct correlation between professional values and nursing performance in clinical settings. It also supports Watson's Theory of Human Caring, which holds that ideals based on compassion improve practical critical thinking and decision-making. **Implications for nursing education and practice.** The study's conclusions have applications for administrators and nursing educators. Through case studies, mentorship, and reflective practice, curricula should uphold fundamental nursing ideals. To improve students' future orientation, educational programs should also include time management instruction, goal-setting activities, and long-term career planning. The transition of interns from student to practicing nurse can be strengthened by designing clinical preceptor programs to foster these qualities during internship training. Institutions may also think about conducting assessments on a regular basis to track

how nursing students' professional values and temporal perspective characteristics are developing.

However, in the finding of Zigzag University just over 1 in 4 nurse interns (42.6%) achieve this. A high level of professional nursing value and a high level of problem solving were present in 46.1% of the sample. Ability Another finding of our study is 62.8% of the group believed that they could succeed with some assistance. Just two person 4.7% with extreme confidence.

Limitations of the Study:

The study has limitations even if it offers insightful information. First, the sample was restricted to a particular institutional and geographic setting, which can have an impact on how broadly the findings can be applied. Second, social desirability bias may be introduced by the use of self-report surveys. Finally, causal inference is limited by the cross-sectional methodology; longitudinal studies are advised for further investigation.

➤ Limited Generalizability;

Nurse interns from particular institutions in a particular area participated in the study. Because of this, the results might not apply to all nursing interns in various institutional, cultural, or geographic contexts.

➤ Cross-Sectional Design;

Data was collected at a particular point in time using a cross-sectional methodology. This makes it more difficult to prove a link between nursing values, future-focused thinking, and problem-solving skills. To evaluate the long-term effects of these variables on one another, longitudinal research is required.

➤ Self-Reported Measures;

Self-administered questionnaires, which could be prone to social desirability bias or erroneous self-evaluation, were used to gather the data. It's possible that participants exaggerated how well they could solve problems or how strongly they held professional principles.

Conclusion:

This study looked into how nursing ideals and future-focused thinking affected nursing interns' ability to solve problems. The results showed that the development of effective problem-solving abilities among nursing interns is highly influenced by both nursing values and future time perspective. It has been discovered that interns with strong professional principles and a clear vision for their future are better equipped to handle clinical obstacles and make wise decisions. The findings highlight how crucial it is for nursing education and training programs to promote a positive, forward-thinking mindset in addition to key nursing values like accountability, integrity, and altruism. These qualities improve interns' clinical proficiency.

Suggestion for future Study:

Future research should examine these connections across other nursing programs and with a larger sample. Further understanding of how interns form their values and time perspectives may be possible through qualitative study. Longitudinal designs could

also look at how these characteristics change over time and affect long-term career performance.

Bibliography

1. yeung M. M.-Y., et al. (2023). "The efficacy of team-based learning in developing the generic capability of problem-solving ability and critical thinking skills in nursing education: A systematic review." Nurse Education Today **122**: 105704.
2. Ashehry, A. S., et al. (2023). "Professional Values and Self-Reported Clinical Competence of Acute Care Nurses in Saudi Arabia: A Cross-Sectional Study." European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education **13**(11): 2697-2708.
3. Bandura, A. (2001). "Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective." Annual review of psychology **52**(1): 1-26.
4. Bayoumy, S. A., et al. (2022). "Critical Thinking Disposition and Problem-Solving Aptitudes among Nursing Interns." Egyptian Journal of Nursing and Health Sciences **3**(1): 434-449.
5. Ciftci, B., et al. (2020). "The effect of internships on clinical decision making and professional values of nursing students." International Journal of Caring Sciences **13**(2): 1230-1239.
6. El-Demerdash, A., et al. (2021). "Problem solving skills and clinical decision making among nursing interns." International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing **8**(1): 304-309.
7. Habeeb, S. (2022). "Importance of professional values in nursing and healthcare." Journal of Practical and Professional Nursing **6**(1): 1-4.
8. Husman, J. and W. Lens (1999). "The role of the future in student motivation." Educational Psychologist **34**(2): 113-125.
9. Kasser, T. and R. M. Ryan (1996). "Further examining the American dream: Differential correlates of intrinsic and extrinsic goals." Personality and social psychology bulletin **22**(3): 280-287.
10. Khater, A. M. M., et al. (2024). "Professional Nursing Value and Problem Solving Ability among Nurse Interns." Zagazig Nursing Journal **20**(2): 144-159.
11. Klumb, P. L., et al. (2022). "Resource-Building Processes Across Life Domains: Father-Child Interactions as Starting Points for Resource Caravans." Journal of Happiness Studies **23**(7): 3263-3283.
12. Osahon, O. J. and O. Kingsley (2016). "Statistical approach to the link between internal service quality and employee job satisfaction: A Case Study." American Journal of Applied Mathematics and Statistics **4**(6): 178-184.
13. Simatupang, R., et al. (2019). "Analysis of Mathematical Problem-Solving Abilities Taught Using Problem-Based Learning." American Journal of Educational Research **7**(11): 794-799.

14. Solvoll, B.-A. and K. M. Heggen (2010). "Teaching and learning care–Exploring nursing students' clinical practice." Nurse Education Today **30**(1): 73-77.
15. Strauss, K., et al. (2012). "Future work selves: how salient hoped-for identities motivate proactive career behaviors." Journal of applied psychology **97**(3): 580.,
16. SÜRÜCÜ, H. A., et al. (2021). "Clinical Decision Making, Problem Solvig and Autonomy for Nursing Students Attending an Internship Training Program: A Comparative Study." MAS Journal of Applied Sciences **6**(2): 481-493.
17. Taylor, C. (2000). "Clinical problem-solving in nursing: insights from the literature." Journal of Advanced Nursing **31**(4): 842-849.
18. Wang, Z., et al. (2024). "Problem-solving ability and future time perspective among the Chinese nursing interns: The mediating role of future work self." Plos one **19**(8): e0308669.
19. Wu, C.-S., et al. (2022). "Effectiveness of a problem-based geropsychiatric nursing clinical internship program." International journal of environmental research and public health **19**(7): 4318.